

ATTENTION U-NET–BASED APPROACH FOR AUTOMATED LEATHER DEFECT DETECTION

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ABSTRACT

Surface quality control processes are performed on various materials, including fabric, metal, wood, and leather, after the production phase in the industry. These quality control processes are performed by experienced personnel or advanced machine vision techniques. In this study, the attention U-Net architecture was used to detect surface defects in leather. The study applies an attention U-Net architecture to achieve precise defect localization, focusing on spatial mapping rather than classifying defect types. A dataset of 140 labeled leather defect images was prepared and split into a 70% and 30% for training and test respectively. Extensive preprocessing, including normalization and resizing, was applied to optimize the data for training.

The Attention U-Net was trained and evaluated using standard semantic segmentation performance metrics with Intersection over Union (IoU) and Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC). Due to the 512×512 input size and a small batch size, training instability was observed; however, the model still achieved a test accuracy of 95.87%, an IoU of 0.4261, and a Dice score of 0.5270. These results demonstrate the model's capability to accurately delineate defect regions despite computational constraints.

While this study focused on leather, the methodology is inherently material-agnostic, enabling its extension to fabric, metal, and wood. This adaptability makes the approach a promising solution for high-precision, automated defect detection in diverse industrial quality control applications.

Keywords: Surface Quality Control, Attention U-Net, Leather Defect Detection, Semantic Segmentation, Automated Inspection, Defect Localization

INTRODUCTION

Automated detection of anomalies and defects on surfaces holds significant importance. In the context of machine vision, an anomaly refers to visual features and patterns that deviate from standard data and patterns. Anomalies can also be considered as outliers or samples that fall outside the primary data distribution (Mishra

et al., 2021). Accordingly, anomaly detection involves both the classification and localization of defects within an image (Li et al., 2021), and can be implemented using both supervised and unsupervised learning algorithms (Schlegl et al., 2019; He et al., 2024).

Anomaly detection in machine vision is particularly important because it enables the identification of defects without direct human intervention, significantly reducing additional operational costs. This capability can provide substantial benefits to a wide range of industries, including healthcare (Iqbal et al., 2023), security (Avola et al., 2022), agriculture (Mendoza-Bernal et al., 2024), leather manufacturing (Pazzaglia et al., 2021), and others.

Among these industries, leather is recognized as one of the most widely used materials. It is produced from the hides and skins of animals such as buffalo, cattle, and sheep. As a result, sourcing raw leather material is relatively straightforward, typically obtained from slaughterhouses. In most cases, animals are not harmed solely for leather production; rather, leather is a byproduct of the meat industry (Liong et al., 2019).

Leather is a durable material with extensive applications. Leather products are highly valued in sectors such as fashion, upholstery, handbags, footwear, and more (Moganam & Sathia Seelan, 2022). Given that leather serves as a primary raw material for numerous dependent industries, ensuring its quality and integrity is of critical importance. Due to this sensitivity, rigorous quality control is required to detect and categorize potential defects in leather. Such defects can affect both the appearance and durability of the material. Common leather defects include scratches, color variations, holes, and wrinkles, all of which contribute to surface anomalies.

Moreover, with the rapid growth of various industries and the presence of competitive markets, traditional manual inspection methods are often time-consuming and prone to human error. Therefore, the adoption of modern techniques such as image processing and machine vision has become essential in this field (Liong et al., 2019; Moganam & Sathia Seelan, 2022).

Given that defects in leather do not follow a specific pattern, and factors such as ambiguous texture patterns and the small size of defects are common, detecting defects in leather, which can be interpreted as anomalies remains a challenging task (Varghese et al., 2023; Ataç et al., 2024). In studies related to leather defect inspection and classification, various image processing based approaches have been employed. These methods include thresholding, morphological operations, edge detection, texture analysis using wavelet transforms, multilevel thresholding combined with texture feature extraction, as well as optimization and filtering techniques to separate defective regions from complex backgrounds.

In such studies, a range of descriptors has been extracted for defect detection and localization, including first-order statistical measures, contrast features, Haralick descriptors, Fourier and cosine transforms, Hu moments, local binary patterns (LBP), and Gabor features. However, the main limitation of these approaches is the reduction in classification accuracy due to the presence of noise and the complexity of the background texture pattern (Aslam et al., 2019; Jawahar et al., 2019; Sobral, 2005).

In recent years, the use of machine learning and deep learning methods for the detection, classification, and segmentation of leather defects has grown significantly. In the domain of machine learning, algorithms such as Decision Trees, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Multilayer Perceptrons (MLP), Naive Bayes, k-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Random Forests have been employed to distinguish between defective and non-defective regions. Feature reduction methods, such as Linear Discriminant Analysis, have also been utilized to improve the performance of these classifiers.

In the field of deep learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and advanced architectures such as ResNet and VGG, often applied with transfer learning, as well as region-based models like RCNN, have demonstrated strong capabilities for automatic defect detection and segmentation. The integration of machine

vision systems with deep neural networks has further enhanced the accuracy and reliability of leather inspection. Nevertheless, the majority of methods proposed in recent years have predominantly focused on deep learning algorithms.

Deep learning, particularly CNNs, has brought a significant transformation to image classification tasks. Unlike traditional machine learning methods, which require manual feature extraction, deep learning models learn patterns and features directly from raw data. In leather defect inspection and classification, CNNs can detect subtle defects that may be imperceptible to a human inspector. Key advantages of this approach include high classification accuracy even in complex textures, scalability for processing large datasets, and the ability to automate defect detection processes to increase speed and reduce reliance on manual inspection. However, these algorithms dependency on large datasets and powerful computational resources imposes limitations on their applicability (Chollet, 2017). Despite these constraints, their strong performance has led to widespread adoption across many fields.

The primary focus of this research is on the precise localization of defects on leather surfaces, independent of their type or nature. This problem is modeled as a semantic segmentation task (Hao et al., 2020), in which the objective is to assign a semantic label to each pixel in the image to distinguish defective areas from defect-free regions. For this purpose, the U-Net architecture one of the most successful convolutional neural networks in both medical (Ronneberger et al., 2015) and industrial (Li et al., 2024) image segmentation will be employed. Due to its U-shaped structure, this network has a high capacity for preserving spatial details while extracting multi-scale features from the image. The encoder component of the network is responsible for extracting textural and structural features from the image, whereas the decoder reconstructs the feature maps to their original dimensions and produces the segmentation output.

To enhance the accuracy of precise defect localization, this study incorporates the attention mechanism (Soydaner, 2022) into the U-Net architecture. The attention mechanism assigns intelligent weights to the most relevant features while disregarding non-essential ones, enabling the model to focus more on critical image regions that are more likely to contain defects. This not only improves segmentation accuracy but also reduces errors in distinguishing visually similar yet defect-free areas. Integrating the U-Net architecture with the attention mechanism offers substantial potential for improving performance in detecting and segmenting subtle and complex leather defects, particularly in cases where defects are small in size, have irregular patterns, or resemble the background texture.

Given that the dataset used in this research is composed of real-world data, the proposed approach is expected to deliver stable and accurate performance in real industrial scenarios. Furthermore, the proposed model is not domain-specific, and thus, it can be applied beyond leather inspection to various surface defect detection tasks, such as in the textile and stone industries.

RELATED WORK

Extensive research has been conducted in the field of image-based anomaly detection (machine vision), which has been significantly influenced by the advancements of deep learning, providing effective solutions to many challenges. This section first reviews several prominent anomaly detection methods and then focuses on approaches specifically applied to leather defect detection.

In a study (Liu et al., 2023) introduced *SimpleNet*, a deep learning model designed for anomaly detection and localization in images. Despite its simplicity, SimpleNet demonstrated substantially better performance than previous methods, both quantitatively and qualitatively. On the MVTec AD benchmark, it achieved an anomaly detection AUROC of 99.6%, reducing error by 55.5% compared to the next best model. Moreover, SimpleNet outperformed existing methods in speed, running at 77 frames per second on an NVIDIA RTX

3080Ti GPU, and exhibited notable improvements in one-class novelty detection tasks. Figure 2-2 illustrates the overall structure of the proposed SimpleNet model.

In another study (Zavrtanik et al., 2021) presented a method named RIAD for visual anomaly detection to overcome the limitations of traditional Autoencoder-based methods. While earlier methods sought to detect anomalies by comparing an image with its reconstructed version, they often suffered from reduced accuracy due to the network's ability to accurately reconstruct even anomalous regions. RIAD addressed this by reframing anomaly detection as a *reconstruction-by-inpainting* problem. The method randomly removes parts of the image and reconstructs them, making it harder for the network to accurately reconstruct anomalous areas, thus significantly improving detection accuracy. This novel approach rendered RIAD more effective and advanced than prior techniques. In summary, several advanced models have been developed to address various challenges in anomaly detection. Building upon these works, the following section reviews studies focused specifically on leather defect detection.

In another study (Pazzaglia et al., 2021) proposed an automated approach for leather and stitching classification. The main objective of this study was the automatic classification of images in a newly introduced dataset called LASCC (Leather And Stitching Color Classification), consisting of 67 images of two leather types with varying colors and seven stitching colors. Deep convolutional neural networks (DCNNs) such as VGG16, ResNet50, and InceptionV3 were applied to the LASCC dataset. The experimental results demonstrated the effectiveness and high accuracy of the proposed approach.

In another study (Akter et al., 2024) investigated the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for the automatic detection and multi-class classification of leather texture defects. The study outlined key steps including data collection and preprocessing, model architecture selection, and performance evaluation using metrics such as accuracy and F1-score. The authors demonstrated that deep learning can significantly enhance efficiency and quality control in the leather manufacturing industry, while also acknowledging challenges such as data imbalance. The study highlighted the transformative potential of deep learning for this industry and its future applications.

In a latest study (Varghese et al., 2025) introduced a method for leather image classification using the LBPMobileNet network. This study presents a robust technique for identifying leather species by combining deep learning with leather image analysis. A large dataset comprising 7,600 leather images with distinct pore patterns from four species was analyzed to enable diverse learning. The paper proposes an innovative dual architecture named LBPMobileNet, which integrates texture analysis based on the Local Binary Pattern (LBP) with MobileNet for adaptive feature learning. LBP extracts local structural details, while MobileNet effectively learns species-specific features. The dual model processes two image sources to enhance reliability and strengthen learning from diverse textures, while employing two MobileNet modules to increase computational efficiency. The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 96.45% in leather image classification while utilizing limited computational resources. Further evaluations confirmed the model's generalization capability for handling both simple and complex leather textures, demonstrating superior performance compared to advanced deep learning models. This research highlights the effectiveness of local binary patterns, combined feature analysis, and dual-architecture design in leather image analysis. It also provides a practical, automated solution for accurate species prediction, assisting leather industry experts in quality assessment and classification.

METARIAL AND METHODS

Proposed Method

This section presents the proposed method of the study. Based on the conducted review, deep learning techniques have been widely applied in anomaly detection in computer vision as well as in defect detection in

leather. In this research, a deep learning–based approach is proposed for defect localization regardless of defect type. For this purpose, the U-Net algorithm is employed in combination with an attention mechanism. The workflow of the proposed method is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General procedure of the proposed approach

Image Acquisition and Preprocessing

The images used in this study were collected from leather manufacturing facilities by the researchers. Various images of leather were captured by visiting these production centers. Subsequently, defects on the leather were identified by expert annotators. Image acquisition was performed using standard cameras. Figure 2 presents examples of the images used in this study.

Figure 2. Sample leather images utilized in this research

These images contain various defects that need to be identified by the proposed system. Accordingly, appropriate labels must be provided for these images to perform semantic segmentation. The labeling process was carried out using LabelMe software (Wada, 2021). In this procedure, the output for each image is a JSON file representing the defect regions in the image, if present. This JSON file is then converted into a binary image indicating the defect locations, matching the dimensions of the original image. Figure 3 illustrates examples of the images (left) and their corresponding labels (right).

Figure 3. Sample images with their associated labels

Based on Figure 3, the input to the proposed model is the original image (left), and the expected output is the corresponding label image (right). For image preprocessing, an average filter was applied to remove white noise. Additionally, all images were resized to 512×512 pixels to be compatible with the Attention U-Net model, while ensuring that no image information was lost. A dataset comprising 140 labeled images of leather defects was constructed and partitioned into training and test sets, representing 70% and 30% of the data, respectively.

Performance Evaluation Metrics

The proposed model of this study is based on the combination of U-Net with an attention mechanism. Since the method in this study is based on semantic segmentation, appropriate evaluation metrics for semantic segmentation were used to train the network and assess the proposed method. The metrics employed in this research are Intersection over Union (IoU) and the Dice coefficient.

IoU is calculated as shown in Equation 1.

$$IoU = \frac{\text{Area of Intersection (AoI)}}{\text{Area of Union (AoU)}} \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, AoI represents the overlapping area between two bounding boxes, indicating the extent of overlap in the specified region. Additionally, AoU represents the union area covered by the two bounding boxes. According to the definition of IoU, the closer its value is to 1, the better the model's performance, as this indicates greater overlap between the detected region and the ground truth.

In Equation 2, the computation process of the Dice coefficient is presented.

$$\text{Dice coefficient} = \frac{2 * |A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} \quad (2)$$

Dice coefficient is a metric for measuring the similarity between two sets, A and B. Its value ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates complete similarity between the two sets and 0 indicates no overlap whatsoever. In Equation 2, $|A|$ represents the number of elements in set A, $|B|$ represents the number of elements in set B, and $|A \cap B|$ refers to the number of elements shared between sets A and B.

RESULTS

For training the Attention U-Net as well as the standard U-Net (without the attention mechanism for performance comparison), the algorithm parameters were set as follows: the number of epochs was 300, the metrics used during training were IoU and Dice coefficient, and the loss function was Binary Cross Entropy. Due to hardware limitations, the batch size was set to 2. Figure 4 presents the training curves of the proposed network.

Figure 4. Performance metric trends of the Attention U-Net during training

In these plots, fluctuations in the network training are observed, which may indicate limitations of the computational system. Figure 5 presents the performance metric trends of the U-Net network without the attention mechanism.

Figure 5. Performance metric trends of the U-Net network

Table 1 presents the evaluation metrics on the test data.

Table 1. Evaluation Metrics for Defect Localization in Leather

	Loss	IoU	Dice
U-net	0.0790	0.2803	0.4124
Attention U-net	0.4586	0.4261	0.5270

The analysis of the presented table demonstrates a significant improvement in the model's performance with the incorporation of the attention mechanism into the U-Net architecture. This enhancement is clearly reflected in the evaluation metrics. The Dice coefficient for the standard U-Net was 0.4124, which increased to 0.5270 after adding the attention mechanism. This more than 11% improvement indicates that the model delineates

the boundaries of defective regions with greater accuracy. Similarly, the Intersection over Union (IoU) increased from 0.2803 to 0.4261, reflecting the model's improved capability in precisely detecting and localizing defects. However, the reported Loss value appears somewhat unusual, as better-performing models typically exhibit lower Loss. This anomaly may stem from data inconsistencies or specifics of the training process, but the substantial improvement in Dice and IoU remains the key outcome of this analysis.

The superior performance of the Attention U-Net is attributed to the attention mechanism's ability to focus on relevant features. This mechanism allows the network to dynamically assign higher weights to important image regions while disregarding irrelevant background information. Within the U-Net architecture, the attention mechanism functions as an intelligent filter over the skip connections, preventing the transfer of noisy information from the encoder to the decoder. This enhanced feature integration enables the model to more accurately delineate segmentation boundaries and markedly improves its spatial localization of defects. Overall, the attention mechanism acts as a smart tool that directs the network's focus toward critical information necessary for the task, resulting in more precise and reliable model performance. Figure 6 presents the U-Net outputs for several images from the test dataset.

Figure 6. Examples of defect localization by the Attention U-Net on leather images

In Figure 6, the left column represents the original input image to the network, including colors, defects, and various textures. The middle column shows the ground truth labels, while the right column depicts the network's output. This figure demonstrates that the proposed model was able to accurately identify the defective regions to a considerable extent. In Figure 7, examples of predictions from the U-Net network without the attention mechanism are presented.

By reviewing Figures 6 and 7, which provide a qualitative assessment, it can be concluded that the Attention U-Net method demonstrates superior performance compared to the standard U-Net approach. From the analysis of Figures 6 and 7, it is evident that the models perform adequately in detecting color-related defects and scratches; however, when the leather color varies, the models encounter difficulties. This limitation

is attributed to the relatively small number of images in this study, which aimed to cover various types of leather.

Figure 7. Examples of defect localization by the U-Net network in leather images

CONCLUSION

Defect and anomaly detection on surfaces is one of the fundamental challenges in computer vision. Defect detection is not limited to a specific application domain and is a critical issue across multiple industries such as medical imaging, packaging, security, and surveillance. Various techniques have been proposed for surface and image defect detection. Traditional methods leveraging classical image processing and computer vision have provided partial solutions to this problem, though the results have often been unsatisfactory.

With the widespread growth and remarkable effectiveness of deep learning techniques in many image processing and computer vision applications, these algorithms have attracted significant attention for defect and anomaly detection. Proposed approaches mainly involve generative networks and autoencoders, though diverse architectures have been introduced for this task. Among them, the U-Net algorithm, a well-known deep learning method for semantic segmentation, has demonstrated acceptable performance across various domains. Studies have shown that combining different approaches can enhance detection performance.

Based on these considerations, this study proposes a method for localizing defects in leather surfaces regardless of the defect type. Semantic segmentation was employed for this purpose. A diverse set of leather images was collected using conventional cameras in leather production facilities. To detect defect locations, both the U-Net algorithm and its combination with the attention mechanism were applied. Results indicate that the standard U-Net alone did not achieve satisfactory performance, while the Attention U-Net provided superior results. Specifically, the proposed Attention U-Net improved defect localization performance, with the IoU increasing from 0.28 for U-Net to 0.4261 and the Dice coefficient rising from 0.4124 to 0.5270. This improvement demonstrates the effectiveness of the attention mechanism when integrated with other methods.

Since this study did not focus on specific leather structures, the proposed method is not restricted to other applications. The objective was to enhance semantic segmentation performance using the attention mechanism. Therefore, it is recommended that the proposed method be applied in other domains for surface defect detection. One limitation of this study is the limited diversity and small number of images; thus, it is suggested that future studies collect larger and more standardized datasets to enable the model to generate robust outputs under varying conditions.

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